

A STUDY ON TACTILE STYLE OF PRODUCTS - USING HANDLESS CUPS AS A CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Sensory experience influences the design styles of products and, among the senses, "touch" has the power to influence only next to the sense of "vision". Therefore, this research makes an attempt to construct a model of tactile style of products through the example of cups. Through literature review, we consolidated relevant theories and defined the content of design styles related to the sense of touch. Subjects (8 male and 7 female) with backgrounds in design were engaged in the pre-test and similarity survey for the study of the tactile Imagery. The multidimensional scaling was then implemented to analyze the experiment data. From the results, we found that physical attributes of cups related to tactile style of products include the feature of bump and gap of surface, temperature, and hardness. From the cluster analysis, we found that there are six categories of tactile styles of products and, in the comparison between the distribution of the representative samples of each cluster and the overall samples, we derived seven styles, including decorative, valuable, plain, luxury, elegant, craft, and neutral. Among which, the style of "neutral" falls into the middle of the three imagery factors. This signifies that the imagery inclination influencing this style is rather weak. Therefore, no significant tactile Imagery has been felt. Results of this research will provide a basis for relevant study in the future, as well as a reference that will help the design firms and designers to create and control the attributes of touch-oriented product design.

Keywords: product tactile styles, touch characteristics, Kansei engineering, multidimensional scaling, cluster analysis

INTRODUCTION

Pioneer of product design in Japan, Mr. Masayuki Kurokawa, mentioned, in his book, The Seven Theories

of Product Design, that the 21st Century will be the time of the senses, especially touch. His theory is echoed by marketing campaigns that constantly emphasize sensory experience and texture of the products. This signifies that there are great opportunities for development in this area. In fact, some corporations have identified the possibilities to create design styles from the sense of touch. Audi, one of the most prestigious automotive brands in the world, became aware that the impression of touch has detrimental influence to the buyers; thus, in 1995, an Audi "haptics team", led by Gerhard Mauter, was established. The mission of this team is to use the science of the tactile sensory to give the control components of all Audi's models the same touch sensations, which provide the convenient and comfortable "Audi feel". This is a successful model of molding a product style around the sense of touch, which brought the need for tactile style based products to light as such products had high demand from the consumers who rely more on the sense of touch. Up till this point, relatively little research has explored the subject of touch design and the majority of these studies have focused on exploring the imagery sensations for texture and surface finishes or touch-based identification without use of vision. These have been studies done on the individual touch attribute, but consolidated studies on touch-based design styles are still lacking. Therefore, the aim of this study is as follow: 1. Define the content of tactile styles; 2. Explore the connotation in the formation of tactile style of products and find the connections between styles; 3. Establish a model of tactile style of products.

LITERATURE REVIEW

To clearly define the content of the tactile style of products, we carried out a literature review, especially focusing on the relationship between texture and the sense of touch, to provide us the relevant data to

interpret the effect of texture change to psychological imagery. The latter half of this section will explore the structure of tactile style formation targeting on the relationship between imagery and styles.

TOUCH

Touch is a cutaneous sensation. This cutaneous sense is a process; during which, skin receives external stimulation, such as touch, pain, and temperature. The sense of touch, also known as the sense of pressure, refers to the feeling incurred when the skin surface comes into contact with or under pressure carried by a certain object and can be categorized into (1) active touch and (2) passive touch (Chang, 2009). If compared under the same stimulation from the same object, active touch brings a sharper feeling than passive touch (Yeh, 2004). Pain is a feeling incurred when skin is physically or chemically stimulated or injured. In terms of personal safety, pain acts as a warning; an individual is able to avoid harmful stimulation by reacting to pain. A thermal sense is a feeling incurring from the skin's reaction to changes in temperature; this includes the senses of heat and coldness. In 1918, a group of researchers began a series of systematic and integrated scientific inquiry into the sense of touch. Among them, Weber observed in his laboratory experiment that a person must experience stimulation up to certain intensity before the sensitivity of touch is triggered and this was later named the Weber Law. Webber proposed a concept of touch, which illustrates that, unless a finger is moved across the surface of an object carefully, the shape or texture of their object can not be distinguished by touch. When we move our finger or hand, we can distinctly sense the relative position between the objective and us and this gives us the information regarding the shape of the object.

THE MEANING OF TEXTURE

The term "material" refers to the organizational attributes of a substance. Texture comes from the Latin word "textura" which means weaving, texture, and structure. It refers to the sensory reactions of vision and touch to surface quality, such as rough, fine, soft, hard, dry, and moist. Texture, on one hand, is determined by the internal structure and, on the other hand, comes from the processing means of the material. Since texture must be felt by the sense of touch, the different qualities of a material, for examples, hardness, temperature, moistness, and smoothness, can only be distinguished through contact (Zhou, 2005).

Zhang (1990) categorized the different visual and touch sensations incurred by forms into: dimension, dots and lines, height, shape, thickness, size, shapes of lines, directions, and textures including fineness, surface contour, motion, sharpness, moistness, weight, stimulation of tastes, fluency/solidness, softness, and temperature. Different forms and use of materials of varied texture give people different visual and touch sensations because the inherent texture or patterns of a material have certain effects on people's emotions (Lin, 2007). The most direct feel of "texture" comes from the attributes exhibited by the materials themselves. For example, one of the most commonly used metal, the steel, gives a feel of coldness and rigidity. And if we take it beyond the physical attributes of the materials, we will see that people's experiences accumulated in life also create impressions or feelings towards certain texture (Lu, 2002).

IMAGERY AND STYLES

Imagery is a psychological attribute and, to a certain degree, it has subjective experience. It is also a reemergence of sensory experiences- an association of the attributes of objects made through a series of mental process, such as sense, perception, and cognition, and from the connotations expressed by the objects themselves (Lin, 2002). Peng & Zhang (2000) proposed that there are four characteristics of "imagery": (1) Simulative; (2) Abstract; (3) Changeable; and (4) Manipulable. And "style" refers to a group of people or objects which have similar attributes or appearances and the specific attributes must be unique and clearly distinguishable when compared to other people and objects not classified in the same style. Chen (1997) further interpreted the concept of style into two systematic viewpoints: (1) Style has four basic functions- discriminate among schools, define attributes, exhibit characteristics, and inspire ideas; (2) Style is hierarchical, decomposable, organizational, and independent. Furthermore, from an inspection on the components of forms, we can see (1) Style is formed by two major clusters of attributes- physical attributes and psychological imagery attributes; (2) The unique corresponding relationship between these two clusters of attributes is exactly the basis on which an integrated style is constructed (Gu, 2006). Based on the above discussion, we can see that the differences between "imagery" and "style" lies in that "imagery" is an internal feeling characterized by metal imaging and impression and "style" refers to the apparent

forms, types, and designs. Differences also exist in the forming processes of these two concepts. "Imagery" is a vague impression exists in the brain, which resurfaces in concrete images after intentional reorganization. "Style" presents the uniqueness of an object, which is formed only after a period of time.

IDENTIFICATION OF STYLES

People shape the knowledge of "style" through the process of sensing, identification, and memorizing. Therefore, "style" is a product chosen by human behaviors and has identifiable characteristics (Gu, 2006). Style has four main functions: classification, identification, presentation, and stimulation (Schapiro, 1961; Enkvist, 1964) and, among which, classification and identification are related to recognition of style (Liu, 2006). Chen (2001) used the example of chairs to explore the recognition and identification of styles in Chinese and Western designs. This study indicated that the differences in the style imagery of Chinese and Western designs are caused by the differences in the attributes in forms. Based on which, identification of the attributes is the basis for identification of the forming of a style. Recognition of the attributes relies on how much they are identifiable. The more they are identifiable; the more they can be recognized. Once the similarity and difference are identified, the non-related attribute association can be eliminated. This is the principle of concept forming (Gu, 2006).

Atkin (1974) pointed out that for a style to be recognizable, forming of a style requires not only specific combination of form characteristics but also specific inter-connection of style characteristics. Chan (1994) utilized geometry and topology to induce form change for the purpose of exploring its influence on style recognition. In this experiment, form change in geometry means changes in the ratio of length and width and form change in topology means changes in the objects' spacial positions. Results of this study indicated that the topological relationship between form elements is the key factor that maintains a style (Chuang & Chen, 2004).

PRODUCT TACTILE STYLE

Based on the above discussion, this research makes an attempt to consolidate the correlation between the sense of touch and style; the relevant theoretical structure is presented in Figure 1. This diagram shows that style is formed by the reception of images at the

psychological level and attributes identification at the physical level. Touch, on one hand, forms a tactile imagery through feeling and sensory reception and, on the other hand, carries out the process of identification for the product's attributes, such as texture, pattern, and form. From this, we can deduce that style of a product can be formed through the sense of "touch". Chen (1997) pointed out in his study on the descriptions of product style that form characteristics which construct a visible style can be classified into six major categories: elements of form, association linking the elements, linking relationship, detail treatment, materials, color treatment, and texture. Among which, except color treatment, the rest of the attributes can be identified through the sense of touch. The research literature discussed previously indicated that similar tactile imagery can be created by using identical or similar tactile characteristics. On the other hand, a specific style can be recognized by identifying some shared tactile characteristics among the forms. Then, we may use tactile imagery to define the content of a tactile style.

METHOD AND PROCEDURE

This research began from selecting the suitable product items through a focus group for assessment and screening out representative products for experiment through a questionnaire survey. Following the selection and screening process, a pre-test for tactile Imagery on the sample cups was carried out, which provided the initial information for tactile Imagery towards the cups and an overview on the distribution of cups in the derived tactile Imagery space, which served as the basis for the comparisons done in the latter parts of the research. The second step focused on the morphological analysis of the products for the relevant assessments and analysis later. The third step focused on the paired comparison of the stimuli of cup samples. And the final step focused on deriving the characteristics of the tactile styles and the correlation between styles by using MDS analysis. We have also constructed a style model for the sense of touch with coordination to the pre-test results

Figure 1: Product tactile style theoretical structure

DETERMINING THE REPRESENTATIVE PRODUCT TYPE

To find the most objectively representative product types that identify tactile styles, we first organized a focus group, which is composed of members with practical experience in product design and have high sensitivity towards the touch of products. In the end, we selected ten products for the appropriateness assessment. Furthermore, from the reasons given by the focus group for choosing the products, we derived six assessment principles: (1) Suitability of the touch area, (2) Variety of the touch material, (3) Identifiability of the details, (4) Distinctness of the contour contrast (identification of the tactile origin), (5) insignificant influence of “change of style” on human factors of product use, (6) Safety in touch. These assessment principles and the above ten product categories were then used to design a questionnaire survey. Subjects of the survey include 13 graduate students (8 male and 5 female) from a school of industrial design. And each principle is used to assess each product on a 1-5 point scale. Finally, we chose the product of cups for the experiment because of its highest assessment score. To minimize interference to the sense of touch from user behaviors, all cup products surveyed in this experiment are used through the gripping mode. To unify the basic criteria, we ruled out cup samples that have handles, protruding bases, and cup lids. “Grip cups”, which are used by gripping the cup walls, are identified as the representative product for the study of the tactile styles.

ANALYSIS ON THE FEATURES OF GRIP CUPS

Through discussion in the focus group, which involves actual touching of the grip cups and comparison of the above classification of touch sensory, members of the focus group were requested to list the features related

to grip cups, and the research team later organized the features into the basic categories. Since the aim of this experiment is to explore the correlation between tactile styles and related features, the scope of touch was limited to the most commonly touched areas, mainly the exterior wall of the cups. Variables, including the fringes, bases, and internal walls of the cups, were not explored in this study. In addition, in the aspect of user behavior, this study focused on the touch feels for the grip cups sitting on a table top. Therefore, the weight and thickness of the walls were ignored at this stage. At the end of this morphological analysis session the focus group summarized 12 items and 25 categories of physical properties or form features which may affect the feeling of touching cups, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Morphological analysis of cups

Samples				
	Items		Categories	Assessment
Forms	Circumference of cup indicated by the position of the middle finger	F1	25cm	0.75
	Form of the circle	F2	Round 1/ square 2/ polygon 3/ irregular 4	3
	Profile	F3	Bulging 1/ sinking 2/ straight line 3/ S shape 4/ irregular 5	3
	Angle indicated by the slanting angle of the gripping middle finger	F4	3 degrees	0.23
	Surface crest line	F5	No 0/ Yes 1	1
Physical Properties	Heat conduction	F6	(low warm) 0-1 (high cold)	0.7
	Rigidity and Hardness	F7	(Weak Soft) 0-1 (Tough Hard)	1
Surface Treatment	Texture	F8	None 1/ textured 2/ horizontal patterns 3/ vertical patterns 4/ repeated shapes 5/ irregular shapes 6	4
	Degree of unevenness	F9	(No) 0-1 (highly uneven)	0.95
	Size of the pattern units	F10	(No) 0-1 (large)	0.7
	Distribution	F11	(No) 0-1 (Fully Covered)	0.7
	Smoothness	F12	(Rough) 0-1 (Smooth)	0.95

*The assessment score like ‘0.75’, ‘0.23’, ‘0.7’... is belong continuous variables. The variables range will be transfer to 0-1. So the categories like ‘F4’ (3 degrees) become to ‘0.75’.

SCREENING THE STIMULI OF CUP SAMPLES

We first collected 32 cup samples from a wide scope of designs and recorded the morphological analysis result of each cup based on the Table 1. The last column of Table 1 shows the result of one cup. Following which, we implemented an additional collection of cups to achieve an even and comprehensive distribution of cup samples among all categories of touch features. A total of 45 cup samples were selected at the end of the process. To screen out the representative samples, this research conducted sample similarity sorting and K-Means cluster analysis. Since there are 25 touch

features, we need at least 26 cup samples for valid regression analysis later. We classified the samples into 25 clusters and choose the sample that has the shortest distance from the cluster center from each cluster as the representative sample. Finally, we added a cup to complete the set of 26 cup samples for the experiment, as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Grip Cup Stimulation Samples

TACTILE IMAGERY PRE-TEST

The first step was to establish the vocabularies related to tactile Imagery. We collected relevant vocabularies from the relevant literature and screened out the representative vocabularies through the expert method. The result is shown in Table 2. Following which, 30 subjects (15 male and female subjects between age 20 and 35 and all of them were graduate students of design) were recruited for the touch SD assessment. The feeling of cups was assessed on each imagery vocabulary through the five-point scale. The subjects assessed samples under blindfold and only the sense of touch was used to assess. A researcher placed the samples on a turntable and asked the subjects to touch the samples. During the process, the researcher reminded the subject the corresponding relationships between the scores and the imagery vocabularies verbally.

Table 2 Imagery vocabularies used in the pre-test

Hard - Soft	Practical - Decorative	Glamorous - Simple
Clean-cut - Complex	Heavy - Light	Unique - Common
Cold - Warm	Delicate - Rough	High Class - Cheap
High-Tech - Handmade	Geometrical - Organic	Dislike - Like

SIMILARITY ASSESSMENT FOR THE TOUCH FEELS TOWARDS THE CUPS

At this stage, we implemented a paired comparison on the grip cups, and through the comparison we made an attempt to determine the degree of similarity between cups, targeting the sense of touch. The subject group consists of 15 members (8 male and 7 female ages between 20 and 25 and all of them were graduate students of design). Each subject is tested individually; during the test, the subjects were requested to evaluate the similarity in touch for each pair from the

26 grip cup samples with a scale of 1-10 for the degree of similarity they felt from the paired samples. The higher the degree of the similarity will have higher the scores. The subjects were test under blindfold and the samples were placed on two separate turntables to eliminate influences from other factors, such as vision and weight. A researcher explained the goal, method, and procedures of this experiment first and then requested the subjects to put on the blindfold to compare the two samples with the one at left as the reference sample. The subject answered all questions through verbal interaction and the researcher made records accordingly. After a pair is done, the researcher changes the sample at the right side in order until all samples were compared. During the process, breaks were given depending on the physical condition of the subject. And during the rest, the blindfold was removed and the samples were covered with cloth. The test at this stage lasted for approximately one hour for each subject and each subject took approximately 3 to 5 breaks for 5 minutes each.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

ALSCAL Analysis

We first organized the collected similarity data among cups of the 15 subjects and converted it into dissimilarity data in a square symmetric matrix marked by the each cup sample. Through the ALSICAL analysis on the dissimilarity matrix, we can obtain a perceptual space of the cups. However, the stress coefficients of the derived spaces are relatively high, even for a five dimensional space. We doubted this may be caused by the incongruence among subjects' assessment of similarity. Thus, we tried to delete the data with excessive scores for finding the best goodness-of-fit structure. We have tried various conditions with different thresholds to discard data above a certain number of standard deviation compared to the mean of the set of similarity data. Table 3. shows the result of deriving a two dimensional space (plane) under different input conditions.

Table 3 Stress coefficient correlations for various dissimilarity data structure

Structure of dissimilarity data	% of retention	Stress	RSQ
All	100%	0.1915	0.8046
Under 2.0	77%	0.1566	0.8665
Under 1.75	58%	0.1228	0.9087
Under 1.5	39%	0.0780	0.9659
Under 1.25	21%	0.0272	0.9967

From this table, we found that when the retained

dissimilarity data which has less discretization, the stress coefficient is also lower. When the dissimilarity data discretization state is under 1.5 standard deviation, the stress coefficient falls below 0.1. This indicates that goodness-of-fit of the derived perceptual plane has reached the level of moderate to good. Following which, we calculated and plot the cups distributed in the derived perceptual plane (map), as shown in Figure 3. Table 4 shows the corresponding coordinate of each grip cup sample in this plane.

Figure 3 Derived perceptual plane for grip cups

Table 4 Position coordinate of grip cup samples in 2 dimensions

Sample	Dimension 1	Dimension 2	Sample	Dimension 1	Dimension 2	Sample	Dimension 1	Dimension 2
S01	-0.5174	1.2835	S10	-1.9187	-0.5533	S19	0.1449	0.8223
S02	1.2308	-1.4786	S11	-1.3499	-0.3530	S20	0.2868	0.3321
S03	-1.5683	-1.4087	S12	0.2486	-0.5554	S21	0.0993	0.4553
S04	1.3994	-0.8814	S13	-0.6819	0.3909	S22	-1.4643	1.3140
S05	0.0613	1.1998	S14	0.8033	1.0395	S23	0.7361	-0.8615
S06	1.0461	-1.0264	S15	1.3360	-0.6448	S24	-1.7052	0.0117
S07	0.2959	1.7191	S16	0.1661	1.0581	S25	-0.6101	-0.8316
S08	-1.1633	-1.2135	S17	0.2991	-0.2445	S26	0.2564	1.0657
S09	0.6355	0.6339	S18	1.9335	-1.2731			

Rotation of the Space Axial and its Connotation

To objectively analyze the meaning of axial dimension, we set the physical attributes of the cups as variables for the purpose of discussion. First of all, we analyzed the touch features of the grip cup samples starting from the basis of the existing spatial axial dimension. From the correlation analysis between an axial coordinates of cups and their corresponding values in the measurements of touch features, we may reveal the meaning of the axial dimension. Since the correlation coefficients for most touch features from the analysis remain around 0.5, which is considered not

large enough to deduct the axial meaning, the axes were reasonably rotated. Results show that, in the properly rotated plane, the correlation coefficients of “dimension 2” related to “heat conduction” and “rigidity/hardness” rose to 0.7, which indicates a medium to high level of correlation. And the level of correlation for “smoothness” and “size of pattern units” have also been uplifted, as shown in Table 5. From Table 5, we found that the feature “degree of unevenness” is the only one moderately correlated to the horizontal axis. We further tested whether the horizontal distribution of the grip cups was related to other touch features with nominal scale in nature. Result shows that the horizontal axis of the perceptual plane may have multiple connotations with some touch features which are all related to changes in the forms, as shown in Figure 4. Therefore, the horizontal dimension can be said to be a dimension that is affected by the construct of form. In addition, “heat conduction” and “rigidity/hardness”, which are related to the vertical axis, are the two major physical properties of material. Thus, we can say that the vertical dimension is affected by the physical properties of the material, as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 4 The meanings in grip cup perceptual space axial dimension

Table 5 Correlation coefficient of the grip cup touch characteristics and original axis

Cup Touch features	Pearson Correlation	Degree of Dimension 1 (45°) Sig. (2-tailed)	Pearson Correlation	Degree of Dimension 2 (45°) Sig. (2-tailed)
Circumference of cup indicated by the position of the middle finger	.028	.893	.043	.835
Angle indicated by the slanting angle of the gripping middle finger	.266	.190	-.006	.977
Heat conduction	.076	.711	.708	.000
Rigidity and Hardness	.067	.744	.691	.000
Degree of unevenness	.475	.014	.482	.013
Size of the pattern units	.100	.626	.516	.007
Distribution	.128	.532	-.162	.429
Smoothness	.109	.594	.520	.007

Figure 5 Touch characteristics of grip cup's perceptual space of touch that affects the axial dimension

Figure 6 Ideal points of tactile Imagery in the perceptual space

Overlapping of tactile Imagery and perceptual space

From the pre-test, we derived the opinions on the samples through the imagery vocabularies. Therefore, we carried out a PREFMAP analysis based on the results of the pre-test. Through the similarity and Imagery data of touching cups (treated as preference data) derived from the subjects' reactions to the stimuli in the SD survey, we developed the distribution of the ideal tactile Imagery points and cup samples in the perceptual plane, as shown in Figure 6.

CLUSTERING OF SAMPLES

Clustering of cup samples then was conducted through the K-means cluster analysis based on the standardized grip cup coordinates. By trial and error, we found that the best cluster number is 5. Therefore, we divided our 26 samples into five clusters for the purpose of further analysis. Clustering result is shown in Table 6. We also marked this clustering result on the perceptual map (Figure 7).

Table 6 Perceptual space sample clusters for the sense of touch

Cluster 1		Cluster 2		Cluster 3		Cluster 4		Cluster 5	
Touch Samples	Distance from the cluster center	Touch Samples	Distance from the cluster center	Touch Samples	Distance from the cluster center	Touch Samples	Distance from the cluster center	Touch Samples	Distance from the cluster center
S12	0.08699	S02	0.09831	S03	0.08779	S10	0.11947	S01	0.09727
S17	0.01953	S04	0.03637	S08	0.01543	S11	0.05030	S05	0.03071
S20	0.10617	S06	0.03481	S25	0.10227	S13	0.15652	S07	0.14816
		S15	0.08369			S24	0.05271	S09	0.12726
		S18	0.11091					S14	0.11248
		S23	0.08867					S16	0.01758
								S19	0.05349
								S21	0.13150
								S22	0.23183
								S26	0.03105
Cluster center coordinate									
Dimension 1	0.01	Dimension 1	-0.02	Dimension 1	-0.29	Dimension 1	-0.17	Dimension 1	0.17
Dimension 2	-0.05	Dimension 2	-0.29	Dimension 2	-0.06	Dimension 2	0.13	Dimension 2	0.16

Figure 7 Initial clustering for sample in the touch-sense perceptual space

IDENTIFY THE TACTILE STYLES

From the ideal positions of tactile Imagery in the perceptual map, we found that some corresponding relations between cup clusters and imagery were not optimized for explanation. Therefore, we made some adjustments to the initial clustering result. First of all, in Cluster 5, located at the upper-right corner, positions of sample 1 and sample 22 are closer to the imagery of “glamorous” and “unique”; therefore, we separated them out to make a new cluster and labeled it with the name of “luxury Style”. Most of other samples in Cluster 5, including samples 5, 7, 14, 16, 19, and 26, are distributed towards the upper right corner along the axis of “degree of unevenness,” carry stronger imagery of “organic and “complex”. Thus, we left them in this cluster with the label of “Decorative Style”. The remaining samples in the original Cluster 5, samples 9 and 21, were grouped into Cluster 1. Although some samples in cluster 1 are located the lower-left corner which may have the imagery of “geometric”, overall this cluster is located around the center area of the perceptual map. Therefore, we can interpret it as the “Neutral Style”, which is characterized by cups that are not strong in any of the imagery. Now, let’s move to the upper-left corner, Cluster 4 is there, which is relatively close to the value imagery of “high-class”, “heavy”, and “delicate”; therefore, we named it the “Valuable Style”. Cluster 2 at the lower half, on the other hand, is closer to the imagery of “simple” and “practical”; therefore, we named it the “Plain Style”. Finally, for Cluster 3, which

falls on the left side, although there is no directly corresponding imagery point near this area, but if viewed from the touch features it belongs to the non-linear profile line with steep angle cluster. It offers the sensation for simple and elegant curves; therefore, we named it the “Elegant Style”. For summary, we compiled the adjusted clusters and style names into Figure 8.

Figure 8 Perceptual space of grip cup tactile styles

Analysis on the grip cup tactile styles

Following the adjustment, we conducted a further analysis on the above six grip cup tactile styles. Through the physical touch features and psychological tactile imagery, we can define the attributes and connotations of the tactile styles. Table 7 is a summary of the results.

Table 7 Analysis of the Grip Cup Tactile styles

Grip Cup tactile Styles	Physical Touch Characteristics	Psychological tactile Imagery
 Valuable Style	The surface is characterized by crest lines, non-circular enclosure style (square, polygonal, or irregular shapes). The physical attributes of the material is cold, hard, and smooth.	The product evokes high value imagery, such as hard, high-class, heavy, and delicate.
 Decorative Style	The surface is characterized by high-degree unevenness, small pattern units, and detailed design. The surface finish falls in between smoothness and semi-smoothness and the material is cold and rigid.	This product evokes the imagery of organic and complex decorative form.
 Luxury Style	The surface is characterized by a high-degree unevenness, the material is cold and rigid, and the surface is smooth.	This product evokes the imagery of Luxury and uniqueness.

<p>Plain Style</p>	<p>The surface is characterized by soft, warm, and rough touch characteristics and the profile contour comes close to the linear and circular shapes of a regular cup.</p>	<p>This product evokes the imagery of warmth, roughness, low cost, practicality, and simplicity.</p>
<p>Neutral Style</p>	<p>The form of this product comes close to the original form of a cup. There is no exaggerated unevenness on the surface, the surface texture falls between roughness and semi-roughness, and the material is cold and rigid.</p>	<p>Tactile Imagery is weakened by the conflict in between characteristics; therefore, no obvious imagery has been evoked.</p>
<p>Elegant Style</p>	<p>Large dimension of streamlined curve with smooth surface softens the cold and rigid texture of the material.</p>	<p>This product evokes the imagery of "clean-cut" and "elegant".</p>

CONSTRUCTING A PRODUCT (GRIP CUP) TACTILE STYLE MODEL

To further understand the relationship between the grip cup tactile styles and the perceptual space of touch, we carried out a factor analysis based on the pre-test SD survey results. Three factors were extracted from this analysis, with the variance of 42.28%, 24.76%, and 22.92%, respectively, and with the accumulated explained variance of 89.96%. This result is summarized in Table 8.

Table 8 Summary of factor load after axis rotation

Descriptive Vocabularies	Factor 1 Decorative Factor	Factor 2 Affinity Factor	Factor 3 Solidness & Value Factor
Geometrical - Organic	.940	.016	-.039
Practical - Decorative	.933	-.011	-.286
Clean-cut - Complex	.900	.133	-.159
Glamorous - Simple	-.887	.271	.221
Unique - Common	-.778	.237	.525
High-Tech – Handmade	.712	.589	-.202
Cold - Warm	.034	.922	.217
Delicate - Rough	-.070	.900	.102
Heavy - Light	-.245	-.028	.949
High Class - Cheap	-.333	.397	.785
Hard - Soft	-.101	.641	.688
Eigenvalue	4.650	2.724	2.522
Explained Variance	42.28%	24.76%	22.92%
Accumulated Explained Variance	42.28%	67.04%	89.96%

We then made an attempt to interpret the connotations of the factors from the imagery vocabularies included in each factor and consequently named the three factors as "Decorative Factor", "Affinity Factor", and "Solidness and Value Factor". Finally, we explored the relationship among the tactile styles and factors through overlapping the three Imagery factors in the perceptual space (Figure 9).

Figure 9 The relationships between grip cup tactile styles and imagery factors

From the diagram, we can see that the Valuable, Decorative, and Plain Styles correspond to the Solidness and Value, Decorative, and Affinity Factors, respectively. Based on this, we can interpret that the corresponding factors are the main causes that form the tactile Imagery of the respective style. After which, we examined the Luxury Style, which falls between the "Valuable Style" and the "Decorative Style". The rigid and high-degree unevenness features shared by cups of this style not only evoke the imagery of decorative values but also the feel of high-value. Therefore, we can see it as a result of interactive influence of the "Solidness and Value Factor" and "Decorative Factor". If we explain the "Elegant Style" in the same way, although the cups in this style share the same rigid and cold physical attributes with those of the valuable Style, it evoke a contrast feel of softer values due to its common features of streamlined curve with smooth surface. This is the interactive quality between Solidness & Value Factor and Affinity Factor. Finally, we see that the Neutral Style falling in the center of the three imagery factors. This illustrates that imagery inclination influencing this style is rather weak. Therefore, no obvious tactile Imagery has been evoked. From the above results, we can see that all six tactile styles can be interpreted from the viewpoints of the interactive influence between the tactile Imagery factors. If we continue to deduce based on this principle, the blank space between the Decorative and Plain Styles (the question mark area in Figure 10) may carry a certain tactile style which will be interactively

influenced by both the Decorative and Affinity Factors. It is now left blank simply because samples chosen for this study lack the forms of this style. Therefore, to ensure that an intact product tactile style system can be constructed, we proposed an additional tactile style here. First of all, the touch features for this style must have the physical attributes of warm and soft with a rough surface, and the degree of unevenness is high. Next, the tactile Imagery is complex, rough, and practical since it is simultaneously affected by the Decorative and Affinity Factors. In addition, this area is also an ideal point for the tactile Imagery of “handmade”. With these clues, it became easy to infer that this style must be decorative, yet close to the general public, like the folk crafts. Therefore, we named it the “Craft Style”. Finally, we compiled the above-discussed seven tactile styles and tactile Imagery factors, along with the major touch features that influence the touch feeling into the following Product (Grip Cup) Tactile style Model (Figure 10).

Figure 10 Product Tactile style model

CONCLUSION

Through a discussion of the literature, we organized the theories and defined the content of the tactile styles. The results illustrate that the sense of “touch” is like other senses. Tactile styles can be formed from identifying the differences in the touch features and the tactile Imagery evoked by the touch features can then be used to form the connotations of the tactile styles. In the analysis of the grip cup touch experiment, this research made an attempt to construct a model that interprets the product tactile styles. Results of this research are summarized in as follows:

- In the perceptual space (plane) of touch, the two major dimensions that affect the tactile styles of

grip cups are “physical attributes of the materials” and “form construct”. Physical attributes of material include “hard/soft” and “cold/warm” and form construct include “high-degree unevenness”, “non-circular enclosure”, and “non-linear profile line with steep angle”.

- The tactile styles of the grip cups in the perceptual plane can be clustered into the: Valuable, Decorative, Plain, Luxury, Elegant, Neutral, and Craft styles.
- Hard/rigid, cold, and smooth touch sensations give the imagery of unique, high class, and high-value, but create a sense of distance. Soft, warm, and rough sensations give an impression of simple and rough and bring the product closer to people; such product have higher affinity to people.
- When the surface texture of the grip cups has high-degree unevenness, the larger the pattern units are, the more glamorous the product is felt; and the smaller the pattern units are, the more decorative feeling is given.
- Rough surface and large curvaceous surface give the imagery of warmth and softness; the perception in value is lowered but affinity is increased.

In the product tactile style model, the tactile styles correspond to the physical touch features, and include the degree of unevenness, coldness/warmth, and softness/hardness. And the names of tactile styles derived may vary from product to product. For grip cups, the corresponding tactile styles include decorative, plaint, and valuable styles. Since these three categories of tactile styles have distinct style characteristics in both imagery and perception, they can be seen as the main tactile styles of grip cups. In addition, the luxury style is the result of influence exerted by the decorative and value factors; the elegant style by the value and affinity factors, and the craft style by the affinity and decorative factors. Finally, the neutral style falls into the middle of the three imagery factors in the imagery space. This indicates that the imagery inclination influencing this style is rather weak. Therefore, no obvious tactile Imagery has been felt. This study illustrates the effect of tactile style in the products. In the future, the relationship between product tactile style and design element can be more broadly and deeply explored to redefine the concept of design style through the sense of touch and bring the tactile styles into applications of a wider scope.

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